

Empirical Study of Scattering from Construction Materials at 10 GHz

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Abstract

The so-called frequency range 3 (FR3) between 7 and 24 GHz has gained wide interest in the wireless telecommunications community. We have investigated wave material interactions with various construction materials by measuring excess losses in the scattering and reflection interactions from slabs of materials at 10 GHz centre frequency. The intention is to get insight into directive scattering patterns of material samples. This information is useful for, e.g., deterministic channel modelling in man-made environments.

1 Introduction

The demand for high-speed, reliable wireless communication has surged with the proliferation of connected devices and the Internet of Things (IoT). To address this need, 6G radio access architecture is envisioned to integrate a network of short-range In-X subnetworks, designed to deliver efficient and robust connectivity in complex environments. These subnetworks, spanning industrial settings, in-vehicle networks, and outdoor-to-vehicle scenarios, require advanced radio channel measurements and modeling, particularly in the mid-bands or FR3 frequencies. The EU SNS JU 6G-SHINE project is dedicated to developing accurate propagation models and channel characterization for short-range communication within these environments.

A key focus of this work is the empirical study of scattering properties of construction materials at 10 GHz. By analyzing how commonly used built-in construction materials such as gypsum, marble, brick walls, plasterboard, and plywood interact with radio waves, this study enhances the understanding of signal attenuation and scattering behavior, which is crucial for precise channel characterization and the optimization of future 6G networks. The angular distribution of scattered power and the ratio between the specular reflected and the overall scattered power are important in deterministic channel modelling.

Scattering measurements from different wall surfaces have been described at mm-wave frequencies in [1] and at sub-THz frequencies in [2]. The material specimen measured in the former publication are partially same as in this work.

2 Measurement and Analysis

Measurement equipment and settings, as well as the data analysis are briefly described in this chapter.

2.1 Materials and Measurement System

The measurement was conducted using a Keysight PNA-X network analyzer and ARRA X820 horn antennas, operating over a 4 GHz bandwidth with a 10 GHz center frequency. The antennas provided approximately 14 dBi gain at 10 GHz, and the transmitted power was set to 2 dBm.

To ensure accuracy, a short-open-load-thru (SOLT) calibration was performed using the Keysight 85033E calibration kit, correcting for cable losses, signal reflections, and discontinuities. Once verified that cable and connector losses were negligible post-thru calibration, an additional free-space measurement was conducted to mitigate environmental interference. The measured parameter was S21 (Tx-to-Rx transfer function), and the setup closely follows that described in [1].

The experiment involved five material specimens of varying thickness: gypsum board (13 mm), marble (30 mm), brick wall (103 mm), plasterboard with internal metal studs (76 mm), and plywood (45 mm). The Tx remained fixed at a 45° incidence angle, while the Rx moved in 10° steps from 10° to 170°, maintaining a constant distance from the material's center. Both antennas were aligned toward the specimen's center, ensuring that the antenna beam footprint remained fully contained within each material. The setup is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Measurement system.

2.2 Data Analysis

In post processing, transfer functions (S21) measured in each angular Rx position were transformed to channel impulse responses (CIRs) using the Fourier transformation after applying the Hanning window function. Separately for each material specimen, the delay bin with the maximum magnitude was selected over all angles and delays. Finally, the magnitude of the channel coefficient of that delay component is considered as the gain of the scattering interaction. By such delay gating we can remove the contribution from the environment and keep only that of the scattering from the material specimen. The delay resolution with the 4 GHz measurement bandwidth is 1/4 ns. Hence, all multipath whose propagation length is not within the ± 3.25 cm range of that path scattered from the centre point of the specimen are removed.

3 Results and Discussions

The resulting scattering gain patterns are illustrated in Fig. 2. Solid lines show the scattering gain as a function of the Rx angle. Dashed lines indicate the direction of reflection, here called the forward scattering direction, and the Tx direction, here called the back scattering direction. We can observe that the highest gains for all materials are around the forward scattering direction and the gains become lower while the scattering angle deviates from it. The scattering patterns are directive for all material samples, i.e., none of them is even close to flat. The marble and brick wall samples show the highest scattering gains while the gypsum and plywood provide the lowest gains. The former are expected to have lowest transmission gains while the latter are rather transparent at this frequency and hence scatter and reflect the least. Please note that this inference is based on the expected material parameters and is partly supported by the absorption measurement performed in the same laboratory after the scattering measurement.

The excess loss with respect to the free space loss is determined by subtracting the antenna gains from the measured Rx power and then calculating the difference to the free space path loss using the path length of the scattered path. The excess losses of different materials both in the forward scattering direction and in the back scattering direction are listed in Table 1. Throughout materials, the forward scattering is substantially stronger than the back scattering, just as expected. The strongest back scattering occurs with the brick wall and the plasterboard with metal studs, similarly as observed with mm-wave frequency measurements in [1]. The back scattering of plasterboard is probably explained by the non-uniform metal structures inside the specimen. The clearly strongest forward scattering, when measured by the excess loss, is observed with the brick wall.

Figure 2. Scattering patterns of measured materials.

Table 1. Excess loss (EL) of the forward scattered path (Snell’s angle) and the back scattered path (Tx direction).

Material	EL forward [dB]	EL back [dB]
Gypsum	33.1	78.3
Marble	31.9	72.0
Brick wall	15.7	43.8
Plasterboard	33.1	55.7
Plywood	44.5	81.6

4 Conclusion

We measured and analyzed the scattering power patterns of several common construction materials at 8–12 GHz frequency band with a 45° incidence angle. The results indicate that scattering is not Lambertian in any case, and the directivity varies depending on the material. Among the tested specimens, plywood and gypsum exhibited the lowest reflection and scattering gains, while brick walls demonstrated the highest gains across nearly all receiver angles. These findings highlight the material-dependent nature of scattering behavior, which is crucial for accurate radio propagation modeling in built environments.

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References

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